

University Administration Models in the World Proposed for Vietnam University

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Abstract:- University administration is one of the issues that requires innovation to meet the demands of education, training, and supply of high-quality human resources in the era of Industry 4.0. This topic has gained much attention and discussion from many educational managers. This article aims to explore university administration models in countries around the world and the current state of university administration models in Vietnam. From this analysis, the article proposes some suggestions for university administration models for universities in Vietnam, with the hope of contributing to the improvement of the quality of higher education to meet the requirements of the new era.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since 2011, there have been many studies and workshops on the necessity of changing the university model to meet the needs of the Industry 4.0 era, as well as the university administration model in the new era. In 2012, at the 3rd session of the 12th National Assembly, the autonomy of higher education institutions was officially included in the Higher Education Law, opening a new era of enhanced autonomy and responsibility for education and university administration in Vietnam.

However, to this day, there are still many conflicting opinions on whether education is a service and whether universities are businesses. This article aims to systematize some university models around the world and propose a university administration model in Vietnam.

II. UNIVERSITY MODELS IN SOME COUNTRIES AROUND THE WORLD

In general, university models around the world have undergone many changes and developments over different periods of time.

A. In Terms of the Target Audience,

The history of development of university education models in the world includes 5 main types of models as follows:

➤ *Elite University Model:*

Characterized by 3 characteristics:

- Rich in talents
- Civilized management
- Strong potential (financial, infrastructure, technology...)

Managed according to the entrepreneurial university model, combining the elite traits of excellent academic management (academic freedom, critical thinking, liberation...) with management as a startup company (action oriented towards end results, fast change and adaptation...)

A few elite universities will still continue to dominate the top of the system and attract top talents as well as large research budgets such as Oxford and Cambridge University in the UK, Paris-Saclay University and Ecole Polytechnique in France, Cornell University, the University of Pennsylvania, Harvard and MIT in the US, and Lomonosov University in the Soviet Union. Currently in Vietnam, Vingroup Corporation has just established VinUni University (as of January 15, 2020) according to this model.

➤ *Mass Higher Education Model:*

These institutions prioritize providing quality education to a large number of middle-class students, closely linked to the job market, and emphasizing globalization. Since the beginning of this century, higher education systems worldwide have been rapidly expanding. Not only middle-income countries, but also low-income countries have been “massifying” – or are in the process of doing so. Higher education is experiencing an unprecedented growth phase in terms of Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER). It is worth noting that the success of “massification” does not bring only positive effects. Along with the growth in quantity, massification also creates a range of issues that need to be widely discussed.

➤ *Elite Higher Education Model*

This could be an online university with world-renowned professors that costs only half as much as traditional universities, such as Minerva School in San Francisco, USA. It could be an institution that provides highly personalized training, developing each individual’s potential with a training program that fits their personal characteristics.

➤ *Local Higher Education Model*

These institutions are closely tied to serving the specific needs of the local community, both in education and research.

➤ *Lifelong Learning Model*

There are many examples of people who dropped out of university but later became world-changers, such as Steve Jobs, Richard Branson, or Mark Zuckerberg. These are people who maintained their lifelong learning despite not

being on a university campus. Depending on their goals and management capacity, institutions can determine the model that best suits their school.

B. From a Management Perspective

There are four models of university governance with different levels of autonomy:

- The state control model, such as in Malaysia;
- The semi-autonomous model, such as in France and New Zealand;
- The semi-independent model, as in Singapore;
- The independent model, as in the UK and Australia.

In the state control model, higher education institutions still enjoy a certain level of autonomy because the state cannot control all of their activities for financial and practical reasons. In the independent model, there are still implicit assumptions about the state's right to hold some strategic control and demand high levels of accountability from higher education institutions.

Neave (1988, 35-37) provides another classification system for different forms of autonomy:

- The Kant model, in which the state only intervenes in certain issues.
- According to Kant, universities are places for training the workforce for the state, and therefore, they must educate workers to use reason to serve the state. Thus, universities must be under state control. On the other hand, universities can only operate well if reason is free from external control. This means that universities must enjoy a self-governing regime so that the process of criticism can occur smoothly. Without a self-governing mechanism, reason cannot be applied freely, and therefore, Kant's university would no longer have a reason to exist. The task of universities is to train republican subjects: people who can use reason freely and have civic spirit in their relationship with the state. It is these enlightened citizens, while performing their duties well, who bring about adjustments for society. And that is the source of progress.
- The Humboldt model, in which the role of the state is supportive. Humboldt University is the model for research universities today, founded in 1810. Up to 29 Nobel laureates have taught and worked at this institution. The Humboldt model has made a significant contribution to the development of science and technology, and the most prestigious universities in the world today are following this model.
- The Napoleon model: The French higher education system (FHE) was formed since the Middle Ages with the creation of the first university, the University of Paris, in the 13th century. Universities during this period were mostly private institutions established by individuals under the recognition of the Pope. After the French Revolution of 1789, the Constitution abolished 22 universities in 1793, then in 1808 Emperor Napoleon restored them and put them under state control, and directed FHE towards vocational training.

- The British model: In the UK, the Ministry of Education only manages education from pre-school to when British citizens are 18 years old, while higher education institutions (HEIs) have full autonomy in management. HEIs actually operate as companies under UK law, with autonomy in spending and managing their budgets, which are provided through research and tuition fees. They prepare their own books, materials, and curricula, and freely compete with their research in the freest environment within the framework of society's acceptance and recognition of UK universities' excellent development. Combining closely with businesses will promote HEIs to develop in a more practical and less theoretical way.

III. CURRENT SITUATION AND PROPOSAL OF UNIVERSITY GOVERNANCE MODEL IN VIETNAM

In June 2012, the Law on Higher Education of Vietnam, passed by the 13th National Assembly, affirmed the role and degree of autonomy of higher education.

At the International Conference with the theme "Training and Researching on Market Economy of Vietnamese Universities" on November 4, 2016, the delegates agreed: the university can be considered as an enterprise. Higher education industry and service provision is a type of business. The university is the service provider, the student is the customer, but the needs of the students are strongly influenced by the needs of the universities' employers in society.

The application of a higher education management model depends on the specific characteristics of the political institution as well as the governance process in that country. In Vietnam, there have also been many studies on university governance models. For example, the research of Pham et al. (2019) suggests that the influence of mass organizations representing the government on the process of internationalization is quite large and contains many overlaps and complications. For internal universities in Vietnam, departments account for a relatively large number, of which in many universities there are many departments and divisions with the same functions but are divided according to the level of study or the purpose of the study. details lead to complexity in the problem-solving process, confusion or complexity in the handling of administrative tasks.

Therefore, this article proposes a university management model based on the Public University and Enterprise Management models for the following reasons:

- Nowadays, universities are essentially service education and training businesses. As a business, universities must operate profitably. The university must generate revenue, build infrastructure that meets the needs of its customers - students - in the new era of Industry 4.0, the flat world era - the era of deep and wide international economic integration.
- The product of a university:

The input is high school graduates or working people who want to improve their knowledge and skills from university level.

The output is global citizens with a demand for global knowledge, global skills, and global employment, meeting the requirements of domestic and international businesses as well as the needs of society in the new era.

Graduates must have critical thinking and creativity skills, innovation, the ability to analyze and synthesize information, the ability to work independently and make decisions based on data analysis, and language proficiency. The university must be a place that leads thinking and motivates students to be creative, connecting with the market and businesses.

To survive and develop, the university must have specific strategies, objectives, vision, mission, methods, and content to attract students - its customers - in the era of global competition and comprehensive changes brought about by the Industry 4.0 revolution.

So, in order to successfully innovate, the school first needs to build a suitable, dynamic, and effective organizational structure with modern management capabilities. This means that administrators should not only be controllers, but also people who create conditions to support staff and employees to perform their jobs with their highest potential. These are the people who design organizational structures and cultures that focus on creativity, adaptation, and innovation, with continuous improvement.

Some education conglomerates have a closed training model from kindergarten, elementary, middle, high school, college, and post-graduate such as Nguyen Hoang Education Group, and Asia International Education Group.

To make the school's management system flexible and effective, the following solutions are proposed:

- Build an organizational management structure according to a matrix structure.

The matrix structure is a type of structure based on multi-dimensional power and support systems. This structure is suitable for the university model in the new era because it has the following advantages.

The matrix is considered the most difficult structure of all because resources are pulled in many directions. However, this structure can provide both flexibility and a better balance of decision-making (as there are two chains of command instead of just one). The matrix model can solve many of the limitations of the traditional decentralized model.

The matrix structure helps managers to flexibly mobilize personnel between departments, contributing to the promotion of cooperation between departments in the organization, enhancing the decision-making, information,

and communication roles of product, program managers, increasing challenges and attracting the attention of employees, and providing in-depth knowledge of different projects, products, and programs.

- Using management software in student management, human resource management and curriculum innovation management. Digital management covers technology, human resources, and work processes. When businesses undergo digital transformation, human resource management becomes a leader in that digital organization, developing new generation workforce, applying technology to change the way we work and collaborate, making work easier and less costly.

Developing a training program that follows the trend of global citizenship education for society. Therefore, regardless of the major or field of study, students need to learn general foreign languages, information technology, Industry 4.0, digital skills, management studies, and soft skills. In addition, universities need to open new majors and fields of study to meet labor demand in the new era, such as Digital Marketing, Multi-media Communication Management, Tourism Management for Business Administration.

- Building a closer relationship between the University and the Business to provide the right and sufficient quality workforce that meets the annual plan of the Business; conduct scientific research, project development, and strategy building according to the Business's order and organize semesters for students at the Business (instead of internships as currently done, students come to the business to practice theory and write reports).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The Fourth Industrial Revolution with the breakthroughs of the internet and artificial intelligence is changing every aspect of economic and social life, and strongly impacting businesses. It is crucial and necessary to identify the public university model and the university management model according to the business model. This will help universities to be proactive and creative in innovating strategies, building programs, content, training methods, and suitable and effective activities in the new era.

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